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۲۰۲۰

پروفیسر (ڈاکٹر) ارشد مسعود ہاشمی

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URDU STUDIES
Bilingual Kitabi Silsila 2

پروفیسر (ڈاکٹر) ارشد مسعود ہاشمی

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2020

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On Translating Ghalib

Prof. Arshad Masood Hashmi

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As the 19th century advanced, India witnessed the collapse of a millennia old composite culture, and as the pace of change accelerated the age of vicissitudes, turmoil, turbulence, transition and uncertainty produced an unusual literary figure in the language that was loathed by the gentries. Mirza Asadullah Beg Khan (1797-1869), known to the world by his pseudonym, Ghalib (or Asad) was soon to be acclaimed as the most important, and by far the most widely appreciated and admired poet of Urdu-language.

Though ahead of his time, Ghalib is himself a metaphor of the city he lived in, and a symbol of the age in which he breathed his last. His poetic genius, apparently a thoroughly emotional and intellectual response to the world around him, is marked by his indifference to and artistic detachment from the world and its critics. He enriched his poetry with shocking paradoxical conceits, sublime imagery, and emotional, intellectual and dramatic intensity. His creativity is attributed to a strong sense of irresolution, mellifluous expression and grandeur of style. Besides an aesthetic urge and mystical diffusion, he employed a remarkably candid, all-encompassing self-portrayal to illustrate the concepts that he wrote about. His poetry, renowned for its utter originality, intellectual paradoxes, strikingly stupefying metaphors, cognitive brilliance, and for being essentially

untranslatable, entralls its readers with its abstractions and obscure expressiveness even in its subtlest forms.

It has been years since Ghalib produced his body of work expressing his views on the social, cultural, moral, and political situations, on love, surrender, beauty, and mystic and spiritual experiences, but, remarkably, the extent to which his writing is applicable and appealing today is shocking and undoubtedly accounts for his ever-growing popularity. His poetry appeals both to those who adore life and its beauty, love and its madness, and to those who are broken. Ghalib's poetry paints life with such vibrant colors that even the gloomy side of life has its own beauty in his distiches. It gives tongue to the feelings and emotions of all and sundry, to the jubilant and elated and to the grieving, afflicted, and dejected. Reading his poetry today we find that despite the passage of time and the successive waves of changes in the way in which so many subjects are viewed today as compared to the period during which Ghalib wrote, he still manages to strike a chord with readers. We cannot fail to recognize the dramatic differences in terms of social, cultural, moral, and political, concepts and conditions, and yet Ghalib's expressions still touch the hearts of his readers with an intensity that makes light of the passage of years and the changes they have wrought.

The grandiose of his metaphors and images is derived from the roots he belonged to. The ancestors of Ghalib migrated to India from Transoxiana. That Achaemenian past had always been a matter of great pride for this Turk who, even on his death bed, relished his inheritance of traits and traditions of the Oxus. Born in Agra, Ghalib migrated to Delhi in 1812/13, and brought with him that old age heritage of Turko-Persian culture. He was soon received as a respectable member of the aristocracy and was privileged to enjoy frequent private assemblies with the erstwhile Mughal emperor, Bahadur Shah Zafar. Ghalib always nurtured high self-esteem and regarded himself as superior to the gentry except when he needed favors to support his passion for wine and gambling. Undeniably a

lifelong egoist, rather narcissist, he was nevertheless an excellent conversationist, - witty, charming, and even generous when enjoying himself socially. Faruqi remarks that true to his Central Asian descent and Turkish seed, Ghalib was always vacillating between tearful piety and excessive pride, between mysticism and materialism, between convention and liberalism, between despondency and hope (K. A. Faruqi, 1992, p.14).

The genre of poetry that achieved its sublimity and artistic brilliance by the creativity of Ghalib is called *ghazal*, a highly aristocratic, classical and rigid form of poetry that was introduced in the Urdu language through Persian. *Ghazal*, the voice of a passionate lover, is a set of four to eight or more semantically independent distiches (two-line verses) in the same meter that have varying subject matters, style, and mood. These distiches are aptly described by Sir William Jones as "Oriental pearls at random strung." *Ghazal*, having close analogies to Arabic poetry, is considered by Christopher Shackle as one of the most striking examples of those "successful cultural artifacts, consisting of a seemingly infinitely adaptable combination of essentially simple elements, which are so characteristic of the Persianate civilization of the eastern Islamic world" (Shackle, para.1). Ghalib's *ghazals* are replete with concrete and kinesthetic imagery, majestic rhythm, and diffusion of vital, liberal cultures of Iran and Central Asia. The startling combination of words and perfectly chiseled idiomatic expressions of chaste Persian and Urdu besides the traits and traditions of Turko-Persian civilization, have carved an exquisite and serene beauty of thought and expression in the distiches of this Goethe of Delhi. He remolded the conceptual elasticity of this genre and revived its "eternal music of the erotic and mystic to imbue it with an all-embracing content" (Zaidi, 1993, p.185) that manifest an unprecedented panoramic thought content of philosophical, social and cultural sweep of emotions and values.

Noted Urdu critic, literary theorist and one of the translators of Ghalib, Shamsur Rahman Faruqi (1981) remarks that Mirza

Asadullāh Khān Ghālib's poetry is "the product of a mind which is in full possession of its reason; Ghālib is an intellectual but one who does not allow himself to become lost to the phenomena of the intellect." He is the metaphysical romantic whose intellectual dissatisfaction took the form of a revolt in his poetry. "The difficulty some encounter in understanding Ghalib does not stem from his use of intricate phraseology but is rather the final link in a process of thought in which intuitive madness is subordinated to a six-dimensional mind" Faruqi (1981). The difficulty that Ghālib mentions in his *ghazal* and to which Faruqi refers in this statement is the sublime ambiguity of Ghālib's poetry. Despite being difficult and terse, and fond of complex ideas, Ghalib's "spontaneous, fresh and intense lyricism changed the prevailing mood of the *ghazal*." (Mujeeb, 2009) His inquisitiveness and sensibility, exotic aesthetical flavor, ambiguity and metaphors of his distiches have made him the most sought-after Urdu-language poet for textual interpretation/commentarial tradition and translation. Most of his translators through the ages, including Ralph Russell and Khurshidul Islam (1969), Sarfaraz K. Niazi (2002), Daud Kamal (1970), and M. Mujeeb (2009), remained content in paraphrasing and transliterating, other of the translators, Tabish Khair (2002), Sufia Sadullah (1975), Ahmed Ali (1973), and J. L. Kaul (1957), for example, preferred transcreating Ghālib. M. Mujeeb (2009) went on to assert that one must paraphrase, one must expand the concentrated expression to convey all that is implied. Yusuf Hussain (1977), in spite of his scholarly introduction to Ghalib's poetry mistranslated many distiches. Kaul, Kamal, and Raina (1984) gave more importance to textual interpretation, and the youngest of the translators, Tabish Khair (2002), did not hesitate to admit that the Ghalib originals in his book were not meant to act as "originals-to-be-translated" but, rather, as "poems-on-which-I-base-my-poems-as-transcreations", and it is the task of the reader "to read both, together and separately, thinking about the convergences and the divergences, and how they relate to contemporary issues." Aijaz Ahmad's translations were described as

an unusual enterprise by C. M. Naim (1996, p.2) as he translated Ghalib engaging seven American poets for the purpose. As far as poetry is concerned, those translations are a good read but besides some of the literal renderings done by Ahmad, it is hard to find the Ghalibian substance in them.

One of the Western authorities on Ghalib, and his outstanding commentator and translator in English, Frances W. Pritchett (2010a), has rightly observed that, "the commentators are for the most part astonishingly unhelpful. Their work is radically limited, often in ways that seem actually counterintuitive. Their explanations don't at all suffice to elucidate for a serious reader what Ghālib is actually doing." Pritchett, adopting Faruqi's method of textual interpretation based on Empsonian technique, adds her own intuitive approach in her online project on Ghālib, *A Desertful of Roses*. She adheres to textual translation and presents many possible renderings on the basis of their textual reading. She is at her best by far when she discusses different layers of meanings inherent in Ghālib's *ghazals*. It is interesting to observe that she tries to ideate the possible connotations of meaning inherent in them. She rightly admits that her translations of the *ghazals* "are the very reverse of literary: they strive to reflect the actual text as faithfully as they can. They are designed not to give you a fine reading experience in English, but to help you get as close as possible to the Urdu. Translating the *ghazals* of Ghalib in a serious literary way is a doomed mission in any case; it's basically impossible." (Pritchett, 2010b) Nonetheless, her translations on one hand and that of all the other scholars on the other hand, the former's work far outweigh the work of the latter. Even then one can never deny that too literal rendering is as much devoid of the flavor of the original as the word-by-word or unit-by-unit translation is when studying a poet like Ghalib, as in the cases of Russell, Mujeeb and Ahmad.

It is interesting to note that the approaches taken by the five great translators of Ghalib, Russell and Khurshidul Islam, M. Mujeeb, Aijaz Ahmad and Pritchett are quite different, and the result

in many cases is a mistranslation that fails to convey certain aspects of Ghalib's grandeur and sublimity. Mujeeb dwells on the poet's intellectual and aesthetic experiences. Russell considers these aspects too but with emphasis on the cultural milieu that projects the speaker of a *ghazal* as the suffering lover, and the poet as passionate lover, and sometimes as the illicit lover. Russell knows but does not emphasize that the *ghazal's* poet is a mystic and philosopher, too. Ghalib's love for the unknown, the unseen and the unperceived beloved and his longings for a union with him/her are the most striking features of his mindset. We must not forget, however, that a commentator is free to air his/her opinion without any reservation. To quote Russell,

“...I, with Khurshidul Islam, see the *ghazal* as essentially the love poetry of a society in which passionate, romantic love is necessarily illicit and is persecuted by the pillars of society; and in it the theme of love between two human beings is paralleled by the experiences of mystic love for God, the Divine Beloved (or, in secular terms, for a high ideal in life) similarly persecuted by the pillars of society. Frances Pritchett and William L. Hanaway on the other hand argue that ‘this characterization is all wrong’... and that ‘any attempt to move from poetic imagery to social reality ... is destined to break down’ (Pritchett)” (Russell, 1995, pp.96-97).

Russell went as far as to say that Pritchett's argument is meant to pay her a compliment she does not deserve (sic). Pritchett's approach is as significant as that of Russell but her reliance on textual reading and lexical meanings, however, narrows the wide metaphorical horizon of Ghalib's poetry while her syntagmatic analysis generates multiple readings of the text. Ghalib was not only that passionate lover involved in relishing his mantic union and separation from the unseen/unknown beloved, he was a social documentarian too. Zaidi (1993, p.192) rightly observes that Ghalib

bears with the traditionally halting response besides demanding reciprocity. He is the poet of frenzied love, "ready to sacrifice," and the one who seeks "fulfillment in leisurely sweet remembrances. At the same time, he is aware of the social milieu and gives tongue to the unresolved conflicts and contradictions of the age."

Ralph Russell's translations are marked by a stress on the literal meaning of the distiches. There are some distiches where he has tried to recreate both the meaning and the form while Pritchett prefers translating meaning with all its subtleties. Whatever the case, the original Ghalib is lost in the process of meaning creation and recreation. Notwithstanding Pritchett's excellent commentaries, in the light of all the aspects of Ghalib's poetic skills, interpretations of some of the most ambiguous verses, and the verses at their best in his typical mindset, need to be reconsidered in order to capture their spirit, meaning, diction, style, glory and grandeur in English. This discourse on translating Ghalib has no end.

While reading/appreciating/translating Ghalib we must bear in mind that he regarded poetry as a form of aesthetic and intellectual self-assertion and self-realization that leads to a negation of everything including the self. This attitude of self-denial has created, within his world of imagery, that metaphysical conceit which is symbolized by a continuous conflict, denial of physical existence, disillusionment, impersonal and intellectual love; and all that wedded with manifold meanings that unfold as morbid wonders. These wonders, sad to say, lose their metaphorical subtlety and effectiveness when they are translated word by word- without efforts being put into select the exact or almost similar expression, diction, and vocabulary. When one attempts translating a poet like Ghalib he must try his best to consider, besides the historical and social context, his intricate grammar, prosody, syntax, and rhetoric, his lexical range and depth, humor and dramatic sense of self.

It would not be inappropriate to cite an example at hand. In one of his subtlest and abstruse verses, Ghalib says:

kishtii-e 'aalam ba tuufaann-e taGHaaful de ke haiN

'aalam-e Aab-e gudaaz-e jauhar-e afsaana ham

Pritchett (2010c), in her commentary, regards this verse as mere wordplay and quotes Frauqi as supporting this stance. She finally comes around to the view that there is obviously nothing except the wordplay in this distich.

There doesn't seem to be any real connection between the 'boat' (and the beggar's bowl) and the 'story'. I asked S. R. Faruqi if he could see anything I was missing. His reply (Sept. 2008) was that in these early verses the young Ghalib sometimes got so carried away by his delight in a 'mischievousness of theme', that he simply neglected to create a desirable amount of 'connection' in his verses (Pritchett, 2010c).

Pritchett's commentary appears to have been a result of her discussions with Faruqi. We wonder why neither of them was able to correlate the inherent meaning in these two lines. This misunderstanding gave birth to a misleading translation as well. Pritchett rendered the distich as:

give the boat of the world to the typhoon of
heedlessness/ negligence, for we
are the world/situation of the water/luster of the
melting/refining of the jewel/essence/art of the
story/narrative

These two lines have no connection with each other, neither semantically, nor pragmatically. Ghālib did love involved expressions, but it does not mean that his distiches were ever, as such, meaningless. If we correlate the images of *kishtii*, *tuufaan*, *'aalam-e Aab* and *afsaana* with the allegory of Noah, the grandeur of this couplet makes itself perceived in a lightning flash. Now, one cannot say that it is a mere wordplay. The young Ghālib has created such a vivid imagery that is strikingly astonishing. Without any

further elaborations or any commentary from my side, I invite the readers to peruse my translation of this distich:

*Do bless the tempestuous heedlessness with the ark of the world
for I am melting in the flow of the essence of the tale!*

Commentaries and textual analysis usually have their own importance, but that is how they make the spirit lost in the translations. Let us take, for consideration, the following distiches of one of the most famous and oft quoted *ghazals* of Ghālib:

1 *sab kahaan kuchh laala-o-gul meN numaayaaN ho ga_iiN
KHaak meN kyaa suurateN hoNgii ke pinhaaN ho ga-iiN*

2 *yaad thiiN ham ko bhii raNgaaraNg bazm-aaraa_iyaaN
lekin ab naqsh-o-nigaar-e ttaaQ-e nisyaaN ho ga_iiN*

3 *sab raqiiboN se hoN naa-KHush par zanaan-e missr se
hai zulaiKHaa KHush ke mahHv-e maah-e kanaaN ho ga_iiN*

4 *niind us kii hai dimaaGJ us kaa hai raaten us kii haiN
terii zulfeN jis ke baazuu par pareshaan ho ga_iiN*

Translating these distiches always remained a passion for the lovers of Ghālib's poetry. Let us have a look at some of the important translations (Pritchett, 2010d):

Verse #1

Ahmed Ali

*Where are they all? Some raise their heads
As tulips and the rose.
What faces must have decked the earth
That under it repose?*

M. Mujeeb

*Though some may reappear as flowers, how sad
to contemplate
The lovely faces that have vanished in the dust!*

Sardar Jafri and Qurratul Ain Hyder

*Where are they now?
(tho' some reappear as tulip and rose),
What faces hide beneath the dust!*

Aijaz Ahmad

*Not all, but only a few, are revealed in the rose
and the tulip;
What faces those must have been that have gone
(been hidden) under the dust!*

Ralph Russell

*Where are they all? Some bloom again as tulips or as roses
There in the dust how many forms forever lie concealed!*

Yusuf Husain

*A few, not all, are manifested / In the rose and the tulip;
What fair faces those must have been / That now in dust are
shrouded.*

S. Rahmatullah

*Behold the tulip and the rose -- / A few fair faces thus revealed!
But hidden in the dust who knows -- / What other beauties lie
concealed?*

David Matthews

*Where are the snows of yesteryear?
The tulip and the rose reveal the faces of a few;
How many lie beneath the dust--those beauties
that I knew?*

Riaz Ahmad

*The Rose, with its redolent petals [sic]
The Water lily with its robe of virgin white
These have surely come to us in transmigration
Of but a few of those
Endowed with sublime beauty and grace.
Some embrace death to sprout again
But most, forever in dust remain.*

Agha Shahid Ali

*Just a few returns from dust, disguised as roses.
What hopes the earth forever covers, what faces?*

Sarfaraz K. Niazi

*Not all, only a few have become evident as tulips and roses;
What images may lie in the dirt that remain hidden from us?*

O. P. Kejariwal

*How I recall / Those days / Of colour / And of pleasure.
But now alas / All that I see / Are flowers and designs / Adorning
the shelves / Of the dusty past.*

Sarvat Rahman

*Not all, of course, a few appear, in the tulip and the rose,
How many beautiful shapes must this dusty earth enclose!*

Gulzar

*Not everything, a few were displayed in that red flower
The earth hid some marvelous faces in her bowels.*

Verse #2

Abdulla Anwar Beg

*We had also in memory many-hued pleasures,
But, now they have become paintings in the niche of oblivion.*

Malik Ram

*We also once knew how to decorate picturesquely the
assembly halls of friends,*

*But these have become now the embellishment of the shelf of
forgetfulness.*

Ahmed Ali

*I too remember colourful and riotous company,
But now they rest as mosaics In the niche of memory.*

M. Mujeeb

*My mind too was once full of memories / Of friendly gatherings,
wine and gaiety,*

*But they are all now delicate trceries / Adorning the dark
corridors of time.*

Daud Kamal

*Took pride in my memories: The raptures of forgotten love
And its faded pictures. But now all that is consigned
To the cobwebbed corridors Of my mind.*

Yusuf Husain

*I, too, recall those gatherings -- / Colourful and gay; but now
The remembrance is like an ornament / Adorning the niche of
oblivion.*

Muhammad Sadiq

*I, too, knew how to arrange colourful festive assemblies,
But they have become now the decoration of the shelf of
forgetfulness.*

Riaz Ahmad

*There was a time When I could recall vividly
A hundred jovialities of our tryst But now, my friend,
With the thickening mist of time, All has obscured slowly*

*Into faded patterns Around the niches
Hollowed out of the walls of my memory.*

Ralph Russell

*I too remembered gatherings rich in all kinds of beauty
Now they are only forms and patterns on oblivion's shelf*

Sarfaraz K. Niazi

*We too had remembered the colorful embellishments of her
assembly,
But now they have become the decorative carvings of the
cupola of amnesia.*

Sarfaraz K. Niazi

Verse #3

Malik Ram

*Generally, everyone hates one's rival, but with the women
of Egypt Zulaikha is pleased that they too fell in love with
Yusuf, the Moon of Canaan.*

Yusuf Husain

*With all rivals she is unhappy, / Except with the ladies of Egypt;
Zuleika is pleased that at the sight / Of Joseph, they were lost.*

K. C. Kanda

*Displeased with all her rivals, but with the Egyptian dames,
Who fell for her moon-like lover, Zuleikha is pleased amain.
Impatient of all her rivals, Zuleikha likes Egyptian dames,
Who fell for her moon of love, so deep were they impressed.*

Khwaja Tariq Mahmood

*Though vengeful as a rule against her rivals' amorous glances
For Moon of Kanaan, Egyptian Venus lauded the ladies'
enchantment*

David Matthews

*My rivals taunt me, but Zulaikha blessed her Egyptian maids
When they became enchanted by the moon of Canaan too.*

Sarvat Rahman

*All are jealous of their rivals, but of Egypt's women,
Zuleikha was content; for they, too, loved Cana'an's rose.*

Verse #4

Abdulla Anwar Beg

*Sleep is his, mind is his and nights are his--
On whose arm thy locks have been disheveled!*

Sufia Sadullah

*His is the Night of sheer Delight!
He--who has your Tangled Tresses,
For Love's Passion--Wild Caresses!*

Malik Ram

*Enviably is his sleep, great his luck and happy his nights
On whose arms your tresses fell and got spread.*

Ahmed Ali

*To him alone belong the nights, Sleep and happiness,
On whose arms your waving hair Has spread in wantonness.*

Daud Kamal

*A million times more fortunate than I Is he upon whose
shoulders Cascade your unravelled silken tresses; Sound
is his sleep and lucid his mind, Serene are his dreams And
blessed his nights.*

Aijaz Ahmad

*To him comes sleep, belongs the mind (peace of mind),
belong the nights On whose arm you spread your hair.*

William Stafford

*Sleep comes, peace, quiet of rest, for one who holds an arm
under your hair.*

Ralph Russell

Sleep is for him, pride is for him, the nights for him

Upon whose arm your tresses all dishevelled lay.

Ahmed Ali

*To him alone belong the nights, / Sleep, and happiness,
On whose arms your waving hair / Has spread in wantonness*

Yusuf Husain

*His is the sleep, the desire, / And his are all the nights,
On whose embracing arm / Thy tresses lie dishevelled.*

Annemarie Schimmel

*Sleep is his, sweet intoxication is his, the nights are his,
On whose arm your tresses lie, dishevelled....*

Muhammad Sadiq

*He alone enjoys a good sleep, mental composure and joyous
nights, Whose arm carries over it thy dishevelled locks.*

David Matthews

*To him come sleep and self-respect, to him belong the nights-
The one on whom you spread your locks, the one who rests with you*

Riaz Ahmad

*That man on whose arm your hair is spread out
Owns three things: sleep, a quiet mind, and night.*

Agha Shahid Ali

*All is his--Sleep, Peace, Night--when on his arm your hair
shines to make him the god whom nothing effaces.*

Sarvat Rahman

*He sleeps truly, he wakes, the scented nights are his,
In whose arms your scattered locks their perfume disclose.*

M. A. R. Habib

*To him belong sleep, peace, the fullest nights
On whose arms, disheveled, your hair flows*

All of these translations are painstakingly and arduously performed, and some of these are excellent pieces of poetry in their own right but, ironically, none of them, except those of Ralph Russell and the one of Annemarie Schimmel, do even scant justice to the original distiches. The translations of M. Mujeeb, Sarvat Rahman and Sufia Sadullah would have been in tune with the original distiches had these translators really paid heed to the verbal and metaphysical complexities, mood, enthralling style and diction, vocabulary, syntactic structure, and had they employed multiple readings of the text, noting always the romantic quest of the poet. Theirs are either plain translations or mistaken/ misleading transcreations. Some of them are too ridiculous to even be called Ghālib's words/thoughts. Ali Jawad Zaidi, a celebrated poet and critic, has also translated these verses, and even his translations are devoid of substance.

Distich#1

Not all but just few revealed themselves in the rose and the
poppy

What beauties they must have been that lie beneath

Distich #3

His is a sound sleep, a profound composure, and his are the night

On whose arms have rolled your waving locks. (Zaidi, 1993, p.194)

In this gloomy background Pritchett's translations appear as the first ever honest renderings that convey, in most cases, the exact textual meaning of the original, while allowing for the multiplicity of meanings in the syntactic and pragmatic context. She often makes the readers' task easier by offering more than one translation of a verse. This attitude, though helpful in understanding a given verse, makes the aesthetic grandeur lost in translation.

Distich#1

1a) not by any means all-- some became manifest in tulip and rose

1b) where [did they] all [becomes me manifest]? some became manifest in tulip and rose

2a) what faces/aspects there will be, that became hidden in the dust!

2b) will there be faces/aspects that became hidden in the dust?

2c) what faces/aspects will there be, that became hidden in the dust?

2d) in the dust, what faces and aspects there will be, that became hidden!

2e) in the dust, will there be faces/aspects that became hidden?

2f) in the dust, what faces/aspects will there be, that became hidden

Distich #2

*even/also we remembered colorful party-adornings
but now they have become ornaments in the niche of
forgetfulness*

Distich #3

all [lovers] may be unhappy with Rivals, but with the women of Egypt

Zulaikha is happy, in that they became absorbed in the Moon of Canaan [Joseph

Distich #4

*sleep is his, spirit/pride/'head' is his, the nights are his
on whose shoulder your curls became scattered/tangle*

(Pritchett, 2010d)

Although the translations of Sarfaraz K. Niazi, Sarvat Rahman, and Frances W. Pritchett are brilliant examples of scholarship, a number of their renderings are unable to show, in the words of Ezra Pound, where the treasure lies notwithstanding that Pritchett, as an interpretive translator, has played the role of guide.

I would prefer considering on all the aforesaid aspects of the Master's poetry when it comes to translating him into English.

Distich #1

*not all withered- some became visible as tulip and rose!
what a myriad of faces would be there, that became concealed in
the dust!*

Distich #2

*I could also thence recall those colorful festive assemblies,
but they are now mere decorative carvings in the niche of oblivion.*

Distich #3

*let all lovers be unhappy with their rivals, however, with the
women of Egypt Potiphar's wife is well-pleased for they got
enchanted by the Moon of Canaan!*

Distich #4

his are the states of sleep, his are the thoughts, his are the nights, on whose shoulders your locks of hair disheveled!

There is a vast world of Ghalib's imagination embodied in his condensed thoughts, a world replete with ambiguous words and elevated expressions, epigrammatic phrases and startling vision that can hardly be accurately translated into English if one doesn't consider varying aspects of his poetry. Most translators stick to explanatory equivalents to convey the sense and reference of a given verse whereas there is no shortage of adequate translational equivalents that carry the essence and substance of such expressions. Mujeeb (2009, p.46) admits that Ghalib's aspiration was the pure aesthetic experience, a glory that is known neither to the lover nor to the beloved, but encompasses both.

The following randomly selected distiches may be considered to help us grasp both how and where these two great translators, Russell and Pritchett, erred:

*banaa kar faqiroN kaa ham bhes GHaalib
tamaashaa-e ahl-e karam dekhte haiN
bandagii meN bhii who Aazada-o-KHud-biiN haiN ke ham
ulte phir Aaye dar-e k'aaba agar waa na hu_aa*

Russell (2000) translated these distiches as:

1. *Taking on the garb of a fakir, Ghalib*

I watch the goings on of the world with a detached air

2. *We serve You, yet our independent self regard is such
We shall at once turn back if we would find the Kaba closed*

Pritchett's version:

1. *1) we, having put on the guise/aspect of the Faqirs, Ghalib*

2) look at the spectacle of the people of generosity

2. 1) *even/also in servitude we are so free and self-regarding that we*

2) *turned and came back if the door of the Ka'bah did not open*

(Pritchett, 2010e)

These translations are neither creative transportations nor do they consider either the emotional content or musical resonance of the verses. Pritchett, in response to Russell's *A Rejoinder to Frances W. Pritchett and William L. Hanaway, Jr.* rightly argues that "...And Ghalib, that notoriously 'difficult' poet, that intransigent aristocrat of the literary world, would never have wished to be known as 'great' for the reason given by Russell: that great poets 'mean what they say, and that somehow this comes across.' Not Ghalib's sincerity or humanism or political correctness, but his ability to create powerful, complex, compelling (and often double and triple) meanings in his poetry is what makes it so fascinating and revelatory to read." (Pritchett, 1996, p.201) We, bearing all these points in our minds, would prefer translating these distiches as:

*Ghalib, we, under the guise of the mendicants,
wonder about the deeds of the munificent people!
so unfettered I am, and conceited, even in servitude, that
I retrace my steps if the House of God doesn't greet me.*

Here is yet another randomly selected distich that lost its magnificence in Pritchett's otherwise excellent translation:

*Husn GHamze kii kashaakash se chhuTaa mere b'aad
baare aaraam se haiN ahl-e jafaa mere b'aad*

She translated this distich as:

*Beauty was left[-off] by the tug-of-war of coquettish-glances,
after me finally the people of tyranny/oppression are at ease, after me*

(Pritchett, 2010f)

Her use of expressions like ‘the tug-of-war’ and ‘after me’ almost snatch away the beauty of this couplet as a whole. I would prefer translating it as:

beauty was unfettered by the conflict of amorousness once I passed away eventually, the oppressors took repose once I passed away!

Colin Flagin, while reviewing *The Lightning Should Have Fallen on Ghalib: Selected poems of Ghalib* translated by Robert Bly and Sunil Dutta (1999), beautifully describes Ghalib as a poet who was “a multi-headed hydra of competing traditions: the devout Muslim who praises Allah, the debauched modern who mulls over the death of God, and the student of Persian poetry who composes in the language of India” (Flagin, para 1). Russell and, to some extent, Pritchett, in spite of their undoubted authority on Ghalib, paid little attention to concepts woven throughout Ghalib’s work and therefore critical to an accurate understanding of his work: the sublimity of love and surrender and beauty and devotion. These aspects of his poetry remained unexplored in their translations and commentaries. Mohammad Taqi (2012) rightly asserts that “within the realm of Sufism, Ghalib apportioned himself a niche that perhaps was neither explored before him nor expounded on after him. This may actually have to do with Ghalib’s well-known desire to remain above the crowd in all his temporal and, indeed, divine quests, thus remaining unorthodox even within the heterodox Sufism.”

Ghalib is the poet whose thought/creative process is an ecstatic and exotic dance of his bewilderment, mystification, astonishment, innocence and madness that borrows its imaginations from various sources of myths and culture accumulated in the primordial images of his collective unconscious. Ghalib is a poet in whose work the madness of beauty and love, if not expressed directly does nevertheless appear subliminally throughout his and his poetry is the essence of Indo-Iranian civilization (Hashmi, 2004, pp.32-33). It can be said with ample substantiation that the manner in which he

formalizes the unique and collective symbolic system by combining different cultural values is unequalled in the world of poetry. Ghalib is stretched like a civilization itself and this is the reason why he lives today as the symbol of a great civilization. He tells the story of the journey of aesthetical values through centuries. It is by him, we get enlightened with the aesthetical vision of the great civilization. He is that symbol by which we can study the synchronization of two greater civilizations onto the soil of India. His aesthetic vision and enlightened thought have abounded the Urdu *ghazal* with an intuitive dynamic vision. In the study of Ghalib's aesthetics we can effortlessly realize the perception of beauty by the help of different aspects of motion and dance. In every experience there are infinite combinations of facets.

In Ghalib's poetry, internal fire and recognition of beloved should not be two different things. Characteristics of fire develop the statuette of beloved and these characteristics in turn build up the internal individuality. Heat, light, darkness, colourfulness, motion, height, expansion, dance, deviation and unconquerable power---these are the ciphers and characteristics of poet's internal persona and also of beloved altogether. These are the fundamental emotional and sensational truths and values of Ghalib's aesthetics. The personas of lover and beloved both are made by these elements and waves. All sensual ideas and sensational aesthetics of color and light, dance, sound and fragrance have relationship with this sophisticated aesthetical archetype, which we call the archetype of fire and woman. Individuality is not different from it. The intensity of unity of idea and experience and the unity of beauty and grandeur have sowed the seed of madness in the poetry of Ghalib. Amazement, drama, curiosity, and fondness are different aspects of innocence and madness and, on the other hand, are also the fundamental ingredients of great poetry. Madness of idea supplies water to the folds of meaning. His poetry leads you to the highest pedestal of the experience of madness. One cannot be able to comprehend Ghalib without completely knowing the stages of madness.

It is impossible for any person who possesses even the smallest sense of rhythm and poetry not to thrill in the grandeur of Ghalib's thoughts and his choice of words. Ghalib undoubtedly occupies a very distinguished place in the annals of master poets, leaving his contemporaries far behind. Ghalib considers himself as the one who despite remaining entangled in the irremediable anxieties of the time "scattered pearls on paper through the strokes of his pen" (K. A. Faruqi, 1992, p.26). The ease and simplicity of Ghalib's expression of thought coupled with his exquisite wordings spontaneously endears his work to readers the world over.

Translating Ghalib, the afflicted Ghalib who had been "a prisoner of loneliness" (K. A. Faruqi, 1992, p.31), with his variety of meanings, levels of meaning, and sheer audacity is the most difficult job for any translator. Like any other great poet, Ghalib's words and his complexity of expression serve to challenge the abilities of the most able translators. Considering this, we had endeavored collectively and objectively to render his work to be understood and appreciated by common readers, namely those readers who are not connoisseurs of literature. The work-a-day life leaves little or no time to devote to the exploration or pursuit of the multiplicity of meanings to be found in many layers of his poetry. We hope that our work here results in increased access to all the subtleties of Ghalib's distiches thereby providing an enhanced appreciation and finer understanding of his poetry by both lay persons and students of literature. Our goal has been to provide ease of access to appreciation of the magnificence of Ghalib's couplets by laypersons. Interpretation of the meanings of his couplets can never be stagnant by virtue of the genius of his language and its multiplicity of potential interpretations, its layering. His genius lay in the edacity of his creations. We just have to take hold of it.

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